

FEATURES OF ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS OF VARIOUS PARTS OF THE SPINAL COLUMN IN CHILDREN AGED 2-6 YEARS LIVING IN THE KHOREZM REGION

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Relevance. The spine is the main part of the musculoskeletal system, its growth and development are analyzed by methods of anthropometric examination, the pathology of the growth of the spinal column leads to the development of various diseases of the musculoskeletal system in children and adolescents in the future. Conducting anthropometric studies of the spine in children by medical professionals and analyzing their anthropometric indicators, prevents the development of various diseases of the musculoskeletal system and their complications. This plays an important role in the formation of a healthy generation in the future.

Modern socio-economic conditions, despite the implementation of measures to modernize the health care system, have an adverse effect on the health of some part of the population, primarily children, therefore, the primary task of health care is to develop therapeutic and recreational measures aimed at a positive change in the health indicators of children and adolescents.

Studies of growth processes in children living in different geographical zones, as well as urban and rural conditions, are of great importance for solving human ecology and medical geography.

The purpose of the study: To study the age-related features of morphometric indicators of various parts of the spinal column in 2-6-year-old children living in the regions of the Southern Aral Sea region.

The material for the study was practically healthy children from 2 to 6 years old living in the Shavatsky district of the Khorezm region. A total of 62 girls and 58 boys aged from 2 to 5 years were examined.

The results of the study and their discussion. The spine of a newborn has the appearance of a gentle arc, concave in front. Bends begin to form only starting from 3-4 months of a child's life, when he begins to hold his head. Initially, cervical lordosis occurs. When the child begins to sit (4-6 months of life), thoracic kyphosis is formed. Later, lumbar lordosis appears, which is formed at the time when the child begins to stand and walk (9-12 months after birth). At the same time, sacral kyphosis is formed. The bends of the spinal column become clearly visible by the age of 5-6, their final formation ends by adolescence, adolescence. With uneven development of the muscles of the right

or left side of the body, incorrect position of students at the desk, athletes as a result of asymmetric muscle work may have pathological bends of the spine to the sides — scoliosis.

The length of the vertebral column of a newborn baby is 40% of the length of his body. In the first two years, the length of the spine almost doubles. Different parts of the spinal column of a newborn baby grow unevenly. In the first year of life, the lumbar region grows faster, the cervical, thoracic and sacral ones grow somewhat slower. The coccygeal department grows the slowest.

Conclusions: In the first two years, the length of the spine almost doubles. Different parts of the spinal column of a newborn baby grow unevenly. In the first year of life, the lumbar region grows faster, the cervical, thoracic and sacral ones grow somewhat slower. The coccygeal department grows the slowest. The bends of the spinal column become clearly visible by the age of 5.

